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Globalisation and Progress: With a Sustainable and Shared Roadmap

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Abstract: Basing on the enriching encyclical Fratelli Tutti by Pope Francis the author reflects on one of the dark cloud mentioned in the letter as “Globalization and process without a shared road map”. In this essay the author highlights the importance and the uniqueness of the Human being and the importance of the right of the individual. The globalization has brought the entire world together but while coming together they have given a rise to greed, possessiveness and selfishness which has turned the sacred human souls into evil. The human beings who were regarded higher than the other living beings because intelligence and creative minds are now left less good than the other creatures. Taking present crisis caused by the evil the author reflects on the suffering of the human being specially the poor and the disabled understood as powerless. The goal is to give due respect and considering everyone equal and a fellow travellers travelling in same boat.

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Introduction

Is progressed globalization beneficiary? If it benefits people, then why there is lot of sufferings and differentiation in human life? Who is the cause for all? Will it be possible to reunite this torn world? Inspired by Pope Francis's call to fraternity I want to show in this article the role of the human being in globalization and its impact on the present generation.

First and foremost, I want to understand the human nature and the abilities of the human being and the developments in all the aspects of life. Secondly I want show how the human being has become proud and gone out of the path in order to become popular. Thirdly I want to come to a conclusion by finding the solution to the problem. Here mainly I want to focus on the invention of Stephen Hawking. And finally want to show that each and every individual is precious and it is our duty to make this world a better living place.

Globalization and Progress

“The uniqueness of humans has been claimed on many grounds, but most often because of our tool-making, culture, language, reason and morality. We have them, the other animals don't, and so the argument goes that's that” says Carl Sagan (n.d.). Human beings are one of the supreme creations of this universe than the other animals, birds, plants and all the living beings. It's true that there are lot of similarities we find in the life cycle of human beings and other living creatures but still they cannot be as effective as human beings. There are three highest categories that makes human as unique and different. First and foremost is the conceptual language. It is true that the language can be spoken by the animal, birds and also by plants. But human being is able to communicate a

conceptual language that is relating to the ideas and the qualities that cannot touch. Secondly human being is creative. If we see in the world of today there are lot of development done by human being, we can see the creative art, paintings, dresses, creative dance styles, usage of techniques and so on. And so to say there is creativity in an animal kingdom too. Still they cannot be compared with creative minds of the human beings. Thirdly we can say that the human being is related to the particular religion, beliefs or the gods and are also performing various rites and rituals based on their beliefs where the animals can never and ever are able to form such understandings (Pandikattu, 2011).

There is a sharing of ideas, resources, cultures and strengthening of economical sate of the country and the relation between nations and also the improvement in the people's welfare and the development of new technologies.

Such is the human being. In the holy Bible we clearly get to read the accounts regarding the creation and developments of human being with their new inventions, skills and ideas gradually starting from a point to the whole mean to say from place to place, state to state and countries to countries the assimilation of economics and society through the flow of information, ideas, technologies, goods, services, capital, finance, and people shortly to say globalization. There is a great impact of globalization on the world. There is a sharing of ideas, resources, cultures and strengthening of economical sate of the country and the relation between nations and also the improvement in

the people's welfare and the development of new technologies.

Outbreak of Tension

We feel proud when we hear about the achievements of the human being in all the aspects of life. One hand there is lot of goodness in the world through globalization but at the same time it has turned to be disaster due to the selfish motives we can say. Especially if we see in this modern world the advanced technology plays a major role in globalization where the means of transport, communication and information has become much easier than ever before. So to say by the influence of this advanced technology the world has become the fast moving world. We want everything fast just like what we call it as fast food. The people have lost patience in everything. There is no patience to listen to the other person, there is no patience to look around to see what exactly is happening, there is no patience even to listen to once own conscience and as a result the value of life is faded out.

The major consequences of globalization today can be of unemployment where the work of the four persons is done by one machine. The other bad impacts can be of the competitive power of the rich countries, the political leaders or the famous businessmen over the poor and the developing countries however they are neglected. Thirdly the impact on the culture and the traditions so to say the discipline of life is lost. There is no room for morality. Life has become like happy go lucky. And fourthly the impact on nature due to the excessive usage of the technology, electronic gadgets and the chemical industries. Basically to say the aim is to gain power, richness and to live a comfortable self centered life free of pain. In an everything sufferers are only the poor and innocent people as Pope Francis makes a statement in his Apostolic Exhortation

that “whenever our interior life becomes caught up in its own interests and concerns there is no longer room for others, no place for the poor” (Francis, 2013: 2).

A Shared Roadmap

As we see the world, the world has no longer left good to live for. We find lot of evil, suffering, the increasing diseases, wars, the global warming, and natural calamities so on. Nobody can ever imagine how the world will be in the future. Being well aware of the potential threats like artificial intelligence, climate change, GM viruses and nuclear wars, Stephen Hawking one of the famous scientist speaks something similar to it. He gives the solution for the present challenge of the world that of leaving this earth and to move to the Mars or the other planets in order to begin new lives over there or else face extinctions (Rincon, 2018). In one way to say his predictions are very much true but in other way moving to the Mars is not the real solution. If at all we move to the Mars, will not Mars too will one day turn just like earth?

“Whenever our interior life becomes caught up in its own interests and concerns there is no longer room for others, no place for the poor” –Pope Francis

So the solution is not in running out of the problem rather in challenging it. So to say the real solution is depends on our individual initiatives to come together to turn this world into a living world. It is not a one man show rather it is the concern of the whole human race. There is a great need of unity. And this unity will not possible until we break the walls that we have erected out of selfishness between the rich and the poor, the able and the disable. The solution is in reaching out to the people keeping in mind

the welfare of the human family just as our Holy Father says “How wonderful would it be, even as we discover faraway planets, to rediscover the needs of the brothers and the sisters who orbit around us” (Francis, 2020:31).

Conclusion

As I have reflected on this enriching encyclical of pope I feel that the greatest challenge in the present world context is human himself. It is true that God the Heavenly Father is the author of our lives. But it is also true that the humans have made themselves the authors of their death mean to say humans are the cause of their own destruction. Today what we can see in the world is only misery. The suffering and the death caused by the Pandemic, wars, conflicts between nations, implement of new laws by the political leaders which are against the welfare of the people specially the poor. Genuinely to say in all the ways the innocent poor people have become the victims. We have regarded them as powerless when we fail to realize that we too are in a same boat.

Finally, the need of the hour is not the project to Mars rather it is the building of the larger human family here on this earth. Human beings are the centre of this universe though rich or poor all are humans belong to the same family of *Homo sapiens*. So each and every individual person has to be respected, honored and are given opportunities to have their rights to live and also to be part of the global activities and the sharers in the resources. Our survival is in our hand. If we are going to continue what we are doing at present surely the

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chapter of human race will be closed one day as per the prediction of Hawking. If not let us be a change, let us be brothers and sisters to our fellow human being. let us be a beacon of light in the lives of the suffering individuals.

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